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ASSESSMENT OF THE STATE AND FUNCTIONALITY OF URBAN GREEN AREAS OF ARMENIA BASED ON THE POPULATION SOCIOLOGICAL SURVEY

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Abstract

An online survey of the presence of green plantations in the cities of Republic of Armenia (RA), the current status and the improvement of their microclimate-regulating, sanitary-hygienic conditions was carried out by the arborist specialists of Institute of Botany of National Academy of Sciences (NAS) after A. Takhtajyan. About 250 RA citizens participated in the survey. The conducted sociological survey made it possible to find out how far the RA citizens are aware of the current conditions, species composition, functional significance and problems of green plantations in their respective cities, which is very important for the science-based decision-making on proper organization of environmental and nature conservation works.

Key words: urban green space, sociological survey, composition of green plantations, vertical greening, improvement of microclimate, citizens perception of green areas

Introduction

Climate change is one of the most serious challenges of the 21st century, which humanity is seriously dealing with. Its consequences are not only in the increase in the frequency and intensity of natural disasters, but it also has a great impact on various branches of the economy, human health and, in general, the sustainable development of human society.

As climate conditions change, adverse weather and climate events are increasing in frequency and intensity, including hurricanes, heat waves, floods, landslides, mud-flows, droughts and wildfires. These weather and climate hazards have a direct and indirect impact on human health and increase the occurrence and spread of non-infectious and infectious diseases and mortality.

Over the last decade, the death rate from air pollution, extreme weather events in urban and vulnerable settlements has been 15 times higher than in less vulnerable areas. Urban areas' poor air quality is a serious threat to human health, causing problems for the respiratory system and cardiovascular diseases worldwide. Every year 3.7 million people die because of air pollution [1-4]. According to the recent research, 37% of human deaths caused by heat attack are due to climate change: Over the past 20 years, the number of heat deaths among people over 65 has increased by 70%. The number of food insecure people increased by 98 million in 2020 compared to the 1981-2010 average. Conservative WHO projections show that by the early 2030s, the effects of climate change on diseases such as malaria and coastal flooding will lead to 250,000 additional deaths per year [5]:

It should also be noted that in large cities, climate change, and temperature are more pronounced [6-11]. Parks, green spaces and water surfaces, which are also

attractive public spaces for city dwellers, have a very strong impact on climate mitigation. They also contribute to the reduction of air pollution. They also help reduce the harmful effects on people's health and quality of life caused by rapid, uncontrolled urbanization. The enlarging of the city infrastructure with natural solutions can alleviate the consequences of climate change and temperature increasing the quality of human life at the same time [12-14].

Increasing the quantity and quality of green spaces helps reduce the effects of short-lived climate pollutants that cause global warming and also contribute significantly to the increase in premature deaths due to air pollution. Parks and green spaces enable people to walk and bike more often to increase their leisure time physical activity. Investing in urban parks, green spaces and waterways is therefore effective and beneficial for health and for mitigation of the effects of climate change. Fountains, pools, lakes and roof gardens also play an important role in mitigating extreme temperatures and the effects of local overheating in cities, saving energy and improving the urban climate [15].

Greening is one of the key issues of current urban development, it has multifaceted significance. Many tree species are endowed with dust-proof, gas-proof, smoke-proof and noise-proof properties. Trees and shrubs absorb 72.0% of airborne dust, 60.0% of sulfur gas and other harmful substances [16; 17; 18; 19].

It is estimated that a 10-20 m wide protective belts of trees reduces smoke air pollution by 20-40%. Trees also have sound-proofing properties, sometimes some deciduous trees reflect sound waves by 70%. According to different authors [20; 21; 22; 23; 19] green areas of cities absorb 26.0% of the total sound energy

falling on these areas. There is a very interesting study about 260 urban green spaces in Armenia, which was also conducted through an online survey [24]:

Taking into account all that, the intensive development and dense population of RA cities, first of all, the capital Yerevan and large cities, there is a need to reconstruct and optimize green areas for general use, offering the use of highly decorative and ecologically resistant plant species, which is also fully derived from the requirements of UN climate change convention and Paris Agreement of 2017 ratified by the Republic of Armenia. The situation of green areas is represented by the typical ratio per inhabitant, which currently, for example, in Yerevan, is only 7.6 m² and is lower than the minimum standard recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) of 9 m² per capita. Shading by tree foliage can significantly reduce the temperature of the shaded surface and the surface above that zone [24]. The management and development of urban green infrastructure, including plant species selection, care, and management of irrigation schedules and intensity regulation, must be implemented taking into account the current and projected challenges of climate change. [26]:

Thus, understanding that the role of green plantings is extremely large and its functions (climatic

regulation, sanitary hygiene, gas protection, noise protection, sanitation, health, etc.) are invaluable, especially in large cities, when carrying out landscaping works, it is necessary to consider the opinion of citizens, take into account their comments and recommendations. The importance of inquiry also lies in the fact that there are problems that sometimes escape the attention of professional group members.

Data collection and methods

Data collection was done through an online survey, which was conducted from February 2022 to December 2023. Online questionnaires were distributed through professional, private and social networks. The data was collected anonymously. Around 250 citizens of RA took part in the survey, 66% of whom are female and 34% male. Citizens from 20 to 50 years old prevailed among the participants. 73% of the respondents are working, 14.9% are students (the majority of them are in the field of natural sciences), and 14.1% are self-employed.

The statistical analyses method was applied to group and perform the interpretation of the collected data. Most of the respondents are from major cities of Armenia: Yerevan - 51%, then Gyumri 14.5%, Vanadzor 9.5%, Vagharshapat 8.7%, etc. (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Place of residency of the participants in the sociological survey

Results and discussions

To the question "Do you have a general idea about the role of green plantings, groves, parks" - most of the respondents said yes (78%), 19.1% partially, 2.9% did not. 51.9% of the citizens rate the state of green plantations in the city as bad, 40.7% as comparatively good and only 7.5% of the respondents rate it as good.

The right selection of species is very important in the creation of green plantations. The decoration and purpose of the given green plantation depends on the

correct selection and combination of plants, in the improvement of microclimatic and sanitary conditions. A number of species are gas-resistant, dust-resistant and can withstand the highly polluted air of large cities, industrial centers: Oak (*Quercus robur*), Plane tree (*Platanus acerifolia*), Ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*), Chenomeles (*Chenimeles japonica*), Rock cotoneaster (*Cotoneaster horizontalis Dene*), Syrian rose (*Hibiscus syriacus*).

Coniferous species have a greater ability to produce phytoncide substances, which have bactericidal properties. Most of them have adapted to unfavorable urban conditions (Juniper and thuja species, silvery spruce), some stand out for their beauty (Horse chestnut (*Aesculus hippocastanum* Laxm), Catalpa (*Catalpa ovata*), Bird cherry (*Padus racemosa*), Canadian redbud (*Cercis canadensis*), etc).

29% of respondents state that they know the types of trees and shrubs grown in their city, 58.5% partially know, and 12.4% do not know.

To the question of whether the conditions created in the green plantations for citizens' recreation and entertainment meet people's requirements, 49.8% of the surveyed citizens indicated partially, 43.6% indicated that they did not satisfy, only 6.6% is to note that it satisfies.

According to the another study related to park availability, accessibility, and service quality, only 17% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with park availability and service quality, and only 50% were satisfied with accessibility. The remaining 5% of the respondents are very dissatisfied, 35% are dissatisfied with the service standards, and 37% expressed a neutral opinion about the accessibility and service quality standards [24; 27].

The majority of surveyed citizens, 92.5%, prefer evergreen and deciduous trees in green plantations. 30.7% of the respondents prefer evergreen and deciduous shrubs, while very few residents prefer natural woody lianas, only 22.4%. Every life form is very important in the creation of green zones. It is hard to imagine green spaces made up of only trees. Due to the correct combination of all the mentioned life forms, it is possible to obtain sustainable plantations that will reduce environmental, health and social risks.

And to the question: is there a need for vertical greening with native lianas in your city, 46.5% of respondents said yes, and 21.6% said no, which is unexpected. At present, there are very few natural woody lianas in the city of Yerevan, and they are almost absent in other cities of the Republic of Armenia. Natural woody lianas are indispensable for vertical and opposite landscaping. Using a very limited land area, they can completely cover the buildings, mitigating the climate. It is especially important in urbanized cities, especially in dry climates, when the temperature can exceed 40°C in the summer months in Yerevan, for example.

What kind of problems do the surveyed citizens see in the green area of their city is presented below (Figure. 2)

Figure 2. The existing problems in the green areas of the city, according to the respondents

Citizens' concern is quite appropriate. Most of the trees in the green areas are of a very mature age, as a result of which they have lost the integrity of the canopy, as well as the functional significance and decoration. The majority of citizens (64.7%) complain about the poor species composition in green areas. The species composition in the city of Yerevan is much richer - about 170 species - than in other cities of Armenia (Gyumri, Vanadzor, etc.). People also value the proper organization of pruning and phytotechnical works. The decoration of trees is no less important. Beautiful and properly selected multi-species plants give an aesthetic look to the green plantations, which makes people spend more time in the green plantations. It leads to an increase in mood, having a psychologically positive effect on a person's health.

Expropriation of fenced land (privatization, long-term lease) is considered one of the most vulnerable problems faced in recent decades. It is no coincidence that the majority of the respondents (86.3%) have a negative view of it. They mainly state that the alienation of green areas has not led to their improvement in any case, on the contrary, tenants and owners have mainly built buildings, profitable facilities and improper care of trees and bushes, which ultimately led to their destruction. One part states that in case of expropriating the territories, the state should be consistent and in the form of a contract, force them to demonstrate proper care. Most of the citizens are of the opinion that green spaces should always be under serious state care and control. Some also offer solutions, if there are insufficient state funds, it is

possible to involve individuals in greening through tenders, instead by providing certain tax concessions, privileges and other incentives.

To the last question, what kind of measures would you propose to increase the level of environmental literacy, most (72.6%) indicated that appropriate programs (trainings) should be organized to spread information about environmental protection, many (60.2%) also indicated quality education and the importance of security, 59.3% think that spreading information about environmental protection through mass media will also help. Some citizens also made interesting proposals. Some believe that in order to increase the level of literacy, it is desirable to provide practical lessons in educational institutions (including junior schools) on the recognition of plants, care and the meaning of each plant, to frequently shoot environmental films and clips, to organize informational campaigns with relevant specialists. Another group of citizens believes that it is not necessary for the whole society to understand environmental issues. Lack of more control in our country leads to such a situation. No one is fined or punished for polluting the green space or damaging the plants. If severe punishments are applied and the media speak out, only people will sober up. And now the feeling of omnipotence formed as a result of mere impunity is speaking among people.

Thanks to this online survey, citizens were also given the opportunity to freely come up with their suggestions for the restoration and improvement of green plantations. Citizens have mostly raised similar issues, which have been summarized and edited by us and are presented below:

- Add, increase public green spaces, also using the roofs of buildings.
- To force the developers and factory owners to have an adjacent green zone with a certain proportion to the area under construction.
- Proper organization of care works: irrigation (switch to drip irrigation system), professionally correct pruning works, phytotechnical measures, etc.
- Providing quality education, conducting various professional seminars not only in Yerevan, but also in regions. To present the role of green areas more often in public hearings.
- Implementation of tree planting works, in which school children, students should be included more and be consistent with their further care works.
- Enrich existing green areas with valuable decorative species.
- Establish more effective and strict legal responsibility for those who damage, destroy and pollute green spaces.
- To ensure the accessibility and quality of green spaces for citizens of all ages and different social classes.

Conclusions and recommendations

Various studies show that urban green areas, in addition to the climate-regulating effect, are also very important from the point of view of people's health. Human interaction with green spaces results in a

number of benefits at both individual and societal levels.

Our studies show that a number of problems that bother specialists coincide with the opinions of citizens. Therefore, the condition of public green spaces should be improved so that they are accessible, pleasant and useful (from a functional point of view) for everyone, regardless of gender, age and social status. Every city should have a sustainable management plan for greening and often involve citizens in these works, which will also increase citizens' awareness.

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